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Collaborative Computational Communities: towards new CCPs, Mid-Project Report

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**Computational Science Centre
for Research Communities**

**Collaborative Computational
Communities: towards new CCPs**

Mid-Project Report

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Introduction and Background

In December 2024 funding was awarded to develop and proliferate the [Collaborative Computational Project \(CCP\)](#) model across research communities within [UK Research and Innovation \(UKRI\)](#), creating a strong and stable landscape of communities to support the concept of research computing software as an infrastructure. This funding was made available via [STFC](#) from [UKRI's Digital Research Infrastructure \(DRI\) programme](#) and is curated by [CoSeC](#).

The purpose of the funding was to enable community scoping to identify and define viable new CCPs that can be incorporated into the existing and rich community landscape, expanding its overall research remit and the reach of the collaborations it can provide.

The following report contains mid-term updates from the six communities funded as a result of the "[Collaborative Computational Communities: towards new CCPs](#)" funding call. Funding began on 1 January 2025 for a period of up to 24 months. The following reports were submitted by 31 December 2025.

Grant Reference	Title	Project Lead
UKRI/ST/B000493/1	CCC-ParaSolS: creating a Collaborative Computational Community in Particulate Solids Simulations	Kevin Hanley, University of Edinburgh
UKRI/ST/B000494/1	Toward a new CCP for Arts, Humanities, and Culture research (CCP-AHC)	Eamonn Bell, Durham University
UKRI/ST/B000495/1	Towards a CCP in Data-driven Computational Mechanics	David Ham, Imperial College London
UKRI/ST/B000492/1	Building a Collaborative Computational Project for Volume Electron Microscopy	Martin Jones, The Francis Crick Institute
UKRI/ST/B000496/1	Building a UK Numerical Relativity Community	Eugene Lim, King's College London
UKRI/ST/B000497/1	Towards a Computational Collaboration Project on Theoretical and Experimental Particle Physics (CCP-TEPP)	Ed Bennett, Swansea University

Foreword

The 2024 *towards new CCPs* call was designed through feedback received from existing communities that creating a new CCP is not easily achieved through funding intended to support an existing or mature community. Given the call was supported through the central UKRI DRI programme it was recognised that support for burgeoning communities to find their identity was necessary.

Dr Stephen Longshaw
CoSeC Director

The call led to the creation of six scoping projects that represent a significant widening for the existing CCP landscape, both in terms of research domains and coverage across UKRI's councils. To ensure that these projects were utilised effectively, two reports to CoSeC were embedded in the call. The first of these is found in this document, with each outlining the outcomes generated in the first year in terms of long-term planning, road maps and identified areas where work directly with CoSeC will now happen.

These new communities provide a rich expansion of UKRI communities, between them they cover new UKRI research areas such as the [Arts and Humanities](#), [Particle Physics and Astronomy](#), as well as expanding the research domains covered within the [Engineering and Physical sciences](#) and the [Biotechnology and Biological sciences](#). This aligns with the UKRI DRI vision of an interconnected and centralised approach for the UK in terms of national compute infrastructure that is utilised optimally across all of UKRI's research remits by organised communities.

The reports provide a clear vision for what each community wants to achieve in the long term, with well-defined roadmaps looking forward. While each have independent goals tailored to suit their community, they all have common threads that take into account key UKRI DRI drivers, including: coherent planning for the adoption (or development) of the use of AI and ML (Machine Learning); ensuring key community codes are developed to be able to effectively utilise GPU platforms; designing data policies and workflows so software and data adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) guidelines.

A key element of these projects is to allow for exploration of what *community* means in practical terms. What a community needs is determined by the people who make it up, so individual focus over the short, medium and long-term varies. Some highlight technical training and knowledge exchange as their priority while others focus on software development exercises such as hackathons. It is clear that all have been able to explore this in-depth, setting them up to be able to create a clear, evidenced workplan in the future.

The next 12 months will be an exciting time for these projects as they bring the technical expertise of CoSeC into their activities. Key challenges and tasks are laid out in the reports, including: GPU acceleration of codes; dataset curation; integration of AI; redesigning software to improve interoperability through community-agreed standards; creation of new underpinning research software infrastructure for use across community codes.

Reports

Please note: these reports are included verbatim as submitted by the Project Lead for each community.

CCC-ParaSolS

[Dr Kevin Hanley](#), The University of Edinburgh

CCC-ParaSolS is a community open to all UK-based scientists and engineers from academia and industry with a common interest in simulating particulate solids (granular materials) for a variety of applications. These granular materials include natural soil deposits, pharmaceutical powders, food ingredients (e.g., salt, flour, agricultural grains), and aggregates and cement used in construction. The most popular particle-scale simulation method is the Discrete Element Method (DEM), although there are many others.

Currently, developments of particulate simulation methods such as DEM happen in discipline silos, inhibiting full exploitation of methodological advancements. CCC-ParaSolS is addressing this issue by creating an overarching community within the UK, steered by community feedback, an Advisory Committee that includes international expertise, and an appointed Management Committee. The aims of CCC-ParaSolS are:

- To build the first and only overarching, multi-disciplinary community in this field in the UK which embeds diversity and inclusiveness in its composition, governance, and activities;
- To promote the use of open-source software for particulate solids simulations, including the open-source DEM codes LAMMPS, MercuryDPM and YADE;
- To promote best practices in validation, benchmarking, and research data management according to FAIR principles;
- To host physical events at different UK locations supplemented by online events for networking, research dissemination, facilitated discussions and training provision;
- To identify major barriers to using open-source codes, and to accessing HPC, in order to take advantage of the UK's digital research infrastructure;
- To deliver bespoke training to lower these identified barriers, prioritising the needs of underrepresented groups, with a specific focus on female participation;
- To identify gaps in granular simulation capabilities which inhibit high-impact scientific discovery and/or slow the transition from workstations to HPC and from CPUs to GPUs to unlock improved energy efficiency and performance via community consultation;
- To develop code benchmarking cases and undertake a high-priority code development project based on this community needs analysis;
- To create a five-year vision for the community, and produce a viable plan for a long-term Collaborative Computational Project: CCP-ParaSolS.

In addition to a comprehensive website (ccc-parasols.ed.ac.uk), CCC-ParaSolS has an active LinkedIn presence (linkedin.com/company/ccc-parasols) and has recently launched a Discourse discussion forum to facilitate community engagement out with Network Events: parasols.discourse.group.

Update on activities that have taken place to this point:

Various activities were undertaken to grow the community to its current size of around 100 members. In the first months, the [website](#) and [LinkedIn profile](#) were created, and a [mechanism to join](#) the community was established. In parallel, members of the core team behind CCC-ParaSolS contacted existing discipline-specific networks with a strong DEM interest, and promoted CCC-ParaSolS through our own contact networks. An [introductory webinar](#) was given in March 2025 on Teams. Since then, we have continued to promote CCC-ParaSolS at conferences and events, aiming in particular to diversify the community demographics, e.g., introducing CCC-ParaSolS to a largely industry audience as part of a [NAFEMS webinar in October](#).

CCC-ParaSolS has held two highly successful hybrid Network Events, encouraging the participation of early-career members at both by reimbursing the participation expenses of in-person attendees. The first Network Event took place [in May 2025 in Edinburgh](#) over three days, and featured a mix of invited presentations, facilitated workshops, panel sessions, networking opportunities, and training on the use of three open-source DEM codes (LAMMPS, MercuryDPM and YADE) delivered by code developers. Almost 40 people attended the event in person with others joining online. The [second three-day Network Event](#) took place in Oxfordshire in October. This included presentations and group discussions on varied topics, and two days of training delivered by experts from EPCC on the use of HPC with ARCHER2 as an exemplar, and running a DEM simulation on ARCHER2 with LAMMPS. This Network Event attracted ~25 in-person attendees and 5–10 online attendees each day.

Key decisions made within CCC-ParaSolS have been informed by the entire community. The Management Committee was appointed in May [through a self-nomination process](#), with constraints to ensure representation from all parts of the community. CCC-ParaSolS identified the high-priority code development project to focus on by soliciting suggestions from the community in August (supported by an online webinar), reviewing these within the Management Committee in September, and ratifying one proposal to proceed with at the second Network Event. The selected project entails adding GPU capabilities to the [MercuryDPM](#) code via the [OPS library](#). Code benchmarking cases are also being developed in CCC-ParaSolS as the other technical focus, complementing benchmarking activities being undertaken in the [ON-DEM COST Action](#) with which many community members are engaged. In future, our recently launched [Discourse discussion forum](#) will provide another platform to communicate within the community.

Next steps:

Particulate solids simulations provide insights into the behaviour of complex granular systems. They have great potential to enable waste reduction and improved efficiency

in manufacturing processes, contributing to the UK's net zero goals and economic prosperity, and reduce risks to life, exacerbated by our rapidly changing climate, caused by mass movement of soil or rock. However, multiple challenges must be overcome to fully realise this potential for economic and societal benefit in the UK. Code developments are essential to exploit modern hybrid computing architectures efficiently and derive performance gains from the integration of mechanistic solvers with physics-informed AI. The physical models underpinning the simulation codes require additional development to capture the complexity of real-world particulate processes quantitatively and reliably for all applications. Rigorous verification, validation and benchmarking require high-quality data which are often lacking.

The roadmap to solution has two strands. Firstly, CCC-ParaSols will promote and accelerate the sustainable development of a suite of high-performance, validated and scalable open-source codes for particulate solids simulations, able to efficiently exploit the current and emerging computing architectures found within the UK's DRI. In 2026, GPU capabilities will be added to the MercuryDPM code with CoSeC support. Targeted developments over the next five years will improve the physical models underpinning the simulation codes. Secondly, CCC-ParaSols will democratise (i) adoption of these open-source codes, (ii) utilisation of HPC, and (iii) uptake of best practices among members in topics related to particulate solids simulations. This will primarily be through the delivery of bespoke training that meets the needs of a diverse and multi-disciplinary community. As a national hub, CCC-ParaSols will also raise awareness of these simulation techniques among decision-makers and in education.

CCP-AHC

[Dr Eamonn Bell](#), Durham University

The goal of CCP-AHC is to support researchers interested in arts, humanities, and culture to use and/or develop research software efficiently and sustainably, while making the best use of UK-based digital research infrastructure (DRI). This includes existing and future high-performance computing (HPC) and AI resources, and advanced computing infrastructures supported by UKRI, as well as those run by UK-based HEIs and other research organisations eligible for UKRI funding.

To achieve this, CCP-AHC engages with a diverse community of academics, digital Research Technical Professionals (dRTPs) including RSEs and software analysts, and academic-related colleagues. Most community members are affiliated with a HEI (e.g. a university), an IRO, or a GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums) institution. CCP-AHC is intended to support all UK-based users of arts, humanities, and culture data and infrastructures, whether they are funded by AHRC or other research councils and funders.

Key priorities for this community are to increase the number of AHC users and AHC use cases for UK DRI. CCP-AHC achieves this by curating and increasing the visibility amongst the community of a portfolio of AHC codes, pipelines, and workflows, which represent a broad range of community applications. CCP-AHC does so by disseminating and implementing the Collaborative Computational Project (CCP) model that has been successfully used by many other scientific software communities over the past several decades. In the coming years, CCP-AHC will deliver software, documentation, and pilot services that implement established applications which have emerged as community needs, including software to improve the digitisation, transcription, organisation and recognition of historic materials (e.g. optical character recognition/handwritten text recognition, automatic speech recognition, document layout analysis, and named-entity recognition) and software for creative technologies (e.g. real-time video).

CCP-AHC will serve as a bridge between the broader AHC community and the growing UK DRI community. The intention is to increase AHC engagement with the vast range of projects, networks, and consultation exercises being undertaken to specify the future data and compute needs of researchers across UKRI. This will improve the quality and relevance of future compute services to our community.

CCP-AHC collaborates with the AHRC-funded iDAH portfolio of DRI projects (which includes the AHRC data services), other UKRI infrastructure investments, and builds international links to comparable initiatives in Europe, North America, and beyond (e.g. the SSH-facing ERICs). We also engage with several cross-council activities, such as the NFCS Network+, CIUK, the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association, UKRI's DRI Congress, and the N8 CIR-sponsored DRI Retreat.

- **Website:** <https://www.ccpahc.ac.uk>

- **Technical outputs:** <https://www.github.com/ccpahc>
- **Publications:** <https://zenodo.org/communities/ccpahc/records>

Update on activities that have taken place to this point:

The first annual CCP-AHC Town Hall was held in Durham on 22 May 2025 with around 25 attendees in-person and 13 online, followed by first Advisory Group meeting on 23 May 2025. Three further regional engagement events were held (Cardiff, 31 October 2025; Edinburgh, 6 November 2025; London, 15 November 2025), which included further requirements elicitation and prioritisation exercises. CCP-AHC Delivery Team members conducted over 50 additional one-to-one/one-to-few stakeholder meetings. These included major AHRC investments including RICHeS, CoSTAR, and TaNC; key staff at other compute DRIs investments (e.g. STFC's IRIS, DiRAC); and prospective community members. In September 2025, the project published an open draft of the CCP-AHC Roadmap (<https://zenodo.org/records/17099176>): a snapshot of community requirements from these meetings. The current version is being revised following the regional events and informs the roadmap below. A second Town Hall is scheduled for Summer 2026.

At time of writing, 24 projects have been submitted to the ongoing open call for codes, pipelines, and workflows. CCP-AHC supported one code owner who was invited to make a full submission to the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) Research Software Maintenance Fund. Training on AI tools for scanned documents using FAIR standards was delivered at University of Luxembourg on 14 October 2025, and more training will be delivered alongside the Town Hall 2026. CCP-AHC is investigating supporting a future edition of the annual Digital Humanities RSE Summer School with network members at Edinburgh, KCL, Cambridge, and Brighton.

Our project site (www.ccpahc.ac.uk) has 150 users active in the last seven days (at time of writing) and accepts contributions from the community. The JISCMail mailing lists for CCP-AHC-ANNOUNCE (announcements and news) and CCP-AHC-DISCUSS (community discussion) have an increasing reach of 126 and 82 members respectively. We have posted regular newsletter-style mailings summarising information from allied DRI projects for our members. Monthly online CCP-AHC Community Forums began in August 2025. Guest presentations were held on Galaxy for Digital Humanities (Daniela Schneider, Galaxy Europe/University of Freiburg) and the PDSI Data Revival service (Jeremy Frey and Sam Munday, Data Revival).

We presented a poster introducing CCP-AHC and sibling project DISKAH at PASC'25 (see below). Project members presented at HPC-SIG, Durham HPC Days 2025, at a STEP-UP network event, and at the DRI Congress 2025. CCP-AHC Delivery Team members have contributed to with the wider DRI and CoSeC community effort, by participating in the CAKE-CoSeC EDI Committee (Bell), hosting the November 2026 CoSeC Community Forum at Durham (Bell), contributing to the CoSeC Conference Committee (Bell), and attending CIUK 2025 (Thiyagalingam, Rodriguez-Echavarria). CCP-AHC indexes the public-facing documentation pages for UK HPC sites

(<https://www.ccpahc.ac.uk/resources/sites/>), lowering the bar to access technical documentation for users of UK-based compute DRI.

Next steps:

Landscape overview The DRI landscape for arts, humanities, and culture (AHC) research is fragmented. Since 2025, CCP-AHC participates in coordination meetings with the AHRC-funded portfolio of DRI projects (iDAH), which includes Archaeology Data Service (ADS), Heritage Science Data Service (HSDS), Museum Data Service (MDS), DiSSCo UK (digitising scientific collections), the Literary and Linguistic Data Service (LLDS), and Enact, a new service for practice and performance data. We also work closely with the AHRC-supported skills and people DRI projects DISKAH and Data/Culture. CCP-AHC team members also routinely co-operate with relevant international initiatives, including the DARIAH, CLARIN, and E-RIHS European infrastructures and the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association. It is expected that CCP-AHC will contribute to several ongoing NFCS Network+ projects, the UKRI ASCEND process, consultation on the AHRC subject-specific data policy, and produce a community statement of need for DRI.

Problem Statement Arts, humanities, and culture (AHC) research shapes society by researching and preserving culture as well as fostering humanism, critical thinking, and creativity, leading to the support of a strong society and its institutions. The main economic contributions of AHC research are to the cultural/memory institutions, creative industries, public policy, and social services (including health and wellbeing), but can be found across all sectors. The computational analysis of digital archives of text, image, sound, video, and physical artefacts promises new insights into shared grand challenges such as social cohesion, climate change, and understanding equality and diversity. Advances in AI and machine learning, combined with improvements in the usability of compute DRI available to AHC researchers, can make vast collections— from galleries, libraries, and museums to web archives— and environments newly accessible to this kind of analysis.

Mere digitisation and storage of cultural artefacts do not produce results; such content often requires transcription, annotation, and/or reformatting before they can be used in research. The diversity of methodological approaches and heterogeneity of the data that is in scope pose serious challenges. However, common tasks such as audio transcription, OCR, and image captioning already have acceptable automated solutions, powered by open-source models and accelerated compute. **The first CCP-AHC grand challenge is therefore to responsibly make established tools available to all UK-based AHC researchers and innovators, regardless of technical skill or institutional resource according to a federated model.** By 2030, no community member should be limited by lack of compute or expertise, laying the foundations for equitable access to more sophisticated computational methods for the analysis of AHC sources.

Collaborative
Computational Project
for Arts, Humanities
and Culture

Roadmap as of December 2025

Bold text indicates key milestones featured on the roadmap graphic

2026

- **CCP-AHC applies for pathfinding allocations on Tier 2 and Tier 1 systems with intention to subgrant to community**
- Produce case study template and guidance for acknowledging CCP-AHC and UKRI DRI support in outputs
- Directory of CCP-AHC codes published and first CCP-AHC codes receive code review (with CoSeC)
- **Pilot services based on reviewed codes and any related datasets go live (with CoSeC)**
- Documentation supporting wider use of submitted codes is circulated to community (with CoSeC)
- CCP-AHC Working Group membership finalised with revised five-year roadmap, and core CCP-AHC projects selected

2027

- CCP-AHC provides access to mature CCP-AHC codes and pilot services, including interfaces for commonly used and established techniques (e.g. audio transcription, batch optical character recognition) through a federated compute infrastructure. **Up to 10 CCP-AHC use cases using national DRI published on CCP-AHC website**
- CCP-AHC contributes first benchmark to UKRI Living Benchmarks
- First CCP-AHC Summer School

- CCP-AHC publishes technical guidance on responsible use of DRI for AHC research

2028

- **UK-based CCP-AHC members and wider stakeholders in AHC research have access to a usable and standardised environment for GPU-accelerated analysis of AHC data, regardless of affiliation and expertise**
- CCP-AHC is established as a UKRI community centre of computational excellence (or similar)
- **CCP-AHC contributes to the compute capability of the iDAH portfolio of AHRC-funded DRI projects**

2029

- **Core CCP-AHC projects refreshed based on feedback and output tracking**
- Update datasets and codes, pipelines, and workflows in standard CCP-AHC environment

2030

CCP-AHC leads internationally in usable, responsible, and FAIR compute for AHC research.

CCP-DCM

[Prof David Ham](#), Imperial College London

This is a collaborative computational community centred around the FEniCS and Firedrake finite element systems. FEniCS and Firedrake are world-leading software frameworks for the numerical solution of partial differential equations (PDEs). These numerical simulations are essential for advancing science and engineering across a very broad range of disciplines.

FEniCS and Firedrake are used to develop solvers in the geosciences (ocean, atmosphere, cryosphere, geodynamics), nuclear fusion (plasma, tritium transport, breeding blankets), physiology and medicine (brain, heart), and many more besides.

FEniCS and Firedrake are revolutionary packages that make it orders of magnitude less expensive to develop sophisticated PDE solvers. Their unique combination of mathematical software abstractions with code generation techniques enables scientists and engineers to compose advanced discretisations, scalable solvers, and adjoint techniques for systems modelled by any PDE. By generating low-level assembly code from a high-level description, the code can be aggressively optimised for the problem and architecture at hand.

The aim of this community is to provide scientists and engineers with the capability to employ the most advanced techniques in forward and inverse simulation from the highest level mathematical interface, without low-level coding. Our community should be able to employ any finite element, any solver, any preconditioner in parallel and at scale. They should be able to solve complex coupled problems, including non-PDE components such as neural networks. They should be able to employ inverse (adjoint) simulations to assimilate real data into their computations and hence to create faithful digital twins.

Our ambition is to relieve application specialists from the costs and complexity of model implementation. They should be able to choose the optimal computational techniques for their problem, without reimplementing. Further, they should be able to easily change even fundamental aspects of their calculation to respond to changes in their scientific challenge, the data available, or the computing hardware to which they have access.

Websites

The CCP's own website: <https://ccp-dcm.github.io/> (.ac.uk domain pending)

Individual project websites:

- <https://www.firedrakeproject.org>
- <https://fenicsproject.org>
- <https://www.firedrakeproject.org/gusto/>
- <https://thetisproject.org>
- <https://fireshape.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

- <https://gadopt.org>
- <https://pyadjoint.org>
- <https://multiphenics.github.io>

Update on activities that have taken place to this point:

The CCP has had an exceptionally active first year. In part this builds on the vibrant, existing Firedrake and FEniCS user and developer communities, but the existence of the CCP has been a catalyst for more organised community building and objective scoping.

Core community events

- **February: Firedrake USA '25.** Around 30 mostly US based Firedrake users met with members of the core team
- **April: Firedrake course at the African Institute of Mathematical Sciences.** We delivered a finite element, Firedrake and machine learning coupling course to around 30 enthusiastic researchers at the AIMS Research and Innovation Centre in Kigali.
- **May: Use Case Hackathon.** 40 developers and users spanning of Firedrake and FEniCS and spanning academia, industry and government met to develop use case documentation. New demonstration applications were documented and published on project websites, and new application capability was developed with industry partners.
- **June: Community scoping meeting.** 20 leading figures from Firedrake and FEniCS user groups met with the CCP team to discuss the high level priorities for the CCP to maximise its value and impact moving forward.
- **June: FEniCS 2025 Conference.** 80 users and developers of the FEniCS system gathered in Groningen in the Netherlands.
- **September: Firedrake '25 workshop.** 35 users and developers of the Firedrake system met in Leeds to present results and exchange ideas.
- **December: CoSeC conference.** Recent developments in FEniCS (work towards GPU support) and Firedrake (differentiable programming and ML integration) were presented at the CoSeC conference in Manchester.

Establishing a CCP

The CCP management committee has met bimonthly throughout the year in support of the activities above. We have established and maintained a CCP web presence, and consulted our external advisers on future CCP activities.

The CCP and CoSeC have supported several research visits within and to the UK, strengthening community ties.

Technical activities

- **Software releases.** Firedrake made new releases to the community in April and September. FEniCS made a release in October.

- **Support.** User support is the most consistent demand from our community. Core CCP team members respond to community support requests on a daily basis.
- **GPUs.** Both Firedrake and FEniCS have conducted scoping work towards our strategic goal of GPU support. FEniCS has released prototype GPU support.
- **Further developments.** Technical development of both packages continues at a rapid pace, including work on coupled problems, ML integration, new discretisations, improved scalable solvers and preconditioners, and enhanced I/O.

Next steps:

Roadmap

Over the next 5 years our goal is a vibrant and growing user and developer community with well-supported and developing software technology for sophisticated digital twins that seamlessly incorporate real data and fully exploit the Next National Supercomputer and the new National Compute Resources. This will make faithful digital twins ubiquitous across high value engineering and high impact physical and Earth sciences.

Community landscape

Multiprocess data-centric computational mechanics underpins a wide span of computational science and engineering, and our large diverse community reflects this. For example, Rolls-Royce design small modular fission reactors, and cleaner, quieter jet turbines. The Met Office develop weather forecast and climate prediction software. UKAEA simulates materials and plasma in fusion reactors. Startup Corintis design bespoke cooling systems individually for each microchip model. The distinctive advantage of our community is our reusable and composable building blocks so that development cost is shared rather than duplicated. We map maths to application without recoding.

People

We will develop our user community by providing training events, but also much improved documentation to facilitate self-directed learning where and when users need it. We will create a continuous development pathway to enable users to achieve the most sophisticated simulation.

We will continuously renew our developer community by supporting users to begin contributing through first contribution pathways such as community hackathons, and backed up by a mentoring scheme encouraging the flourishing of new contributors.

We will reflect and respond to our community through transparent governance into which every member of our community has the opportunity to contribute.

Software Technology

We will achieve full and seamless GPU support. We will improve support for multiple physical phenomena in each material component, and for coupling multiple

components together, including by machine learning. We will enhance our capabilities in data assimilation, including enhanced adjoint (backpropagation) technology and emerging approaches such as parallel in time computation.

Support

We will provide our community with highly professional software on which they can depend. We will issue regular software releases with well-advertised deprecation and transition pathways. We will maintain our use of continuous integration to ensure quality and catch issues early. We will fix bugs in a timely manner, and we will provide ongoing user support via open and accessible public channels.

CCP-volumeEM

[Martin Jones](#), The Francis Crick Institute

Volume electron microscopy (vEM) was named as one of Nature's seven technologies to watch in 2023, and electron-microscopy based connectomics is Nature's method of the year in 2025. With technological advances allowing automated 3D imaging of biological samples at nanometre resolution over scales of microns to millimetres, vEM datasets routinely reach the terabyte regime and require complex computational workflows to reconstruct, process, and analyse the images. Modern tools like next generation file formats (NGFF), AI, and high performance computing infrastructure enable potential solutions to several computational challenges, but such tools are largely inaccessible to the intended end-users (biologists and microscopists). CCP-volumeEM aims to accelerate the adoption of these technologies by coordinating the broad community of stakeholders, providing technical expertise in research software engineering, and providing relevant training, both to developers and end-users.

To achieve these aims, CCP-volumeEM's activities have been divided into three work packages: **Community Building**, **Research Software and Data Management**, and **Training and Skills**.

The community building element of the project is able to leverage several pre-existing networks, such as the volume EM community (volumeem.org), the Royal Microscopical Society (RMS) and BioimagingUK. This provides opportunities for further engagement with related communities, allowing CCP-volumeEM to work with stakeholders from a range of imaging and developer backgrounds. CCP-volumeEM will promote its outputs amongst these networks to encourage sustainable and reproducible science, via guidance on best-practice in software development and data management.

The software and data element of the project will initially focus on pilot projects targeting known bottlenecks in vEM analysis. In particular, we will address the difficulties for non-computational end-users of installing and using modern computational environments and tools, and the technical challenges of integrating the latest tools like NGFF and AI into workflows operating on terabyte-scale datasets. The outputs of these pilot projects will be shared via online resources, community meetings, training courses, exemplar workflows, and hackathons.

The training element of the project will provide resources for a diverse range of stakeholders, from biology researchers with little or no experience in computational methods, through to image analysts and software developers with little experience in the bioimaging domain. Training materials will be disseminated via a mixture of in-person courses, live online courses and online tutorials. A catalogue of these materials will be created, curated, and shared, with guidance given to primary developers of new software tools to create similar materials. A major focus of these training activities will be in providing support and training for software developers, establishing community-led best-practice to ensure long-term sustainability of domain-critical tools.

Website: www.ccp-volumeem.ac.uk (going live Jan 2026)

BlueSky: [@ccp-volumeem.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/ccp-volumeem.bsky.social)

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@CCP-volumeEM>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13308008/>

Update on activities that have taken place to this point:

Early activities were focused upon establishing the current landscape of the vEM analysis community, both in terms of its members, and the software tools in use. For this purpose, a survey was run from May until September, distributed via a range of mailing lists and other communications channels, receiving 63 responses. The responses to this survey were presented at the inaugural CCP-volumeEM community meeting at the Francis Crick Institute in November 2025. The results highlighted the range of software tools in common usage, as well as the current bottlenecks in image processing and analysis in vEM. These insights have been incorporated into the roadmap for the CCP.

The CCP was promoted at various national and international conferences as posters or presentations, including: CCP-EM Spring Symposium (Apr), Gordon Research Conference on vEM (May), CoSeC forum (Jun, Nov), BioimagingUK meeting (Jul), Microscience Microscopy Congress (July), volume EM community town hall (Oct), CCP-volumeEM community meeting (Nov), Crick Bioimage Analysis Symposium (Nov) and the CoSeC conference (Dec).

Software development activities have been carried out by developers at the Rosalind Franklin Institute (RFI), the Francis Crick Institute and CoSeC. Activities at the RFI have centred on the development of a set of Docker containers for commonly used vEM software tools: Fiji, napari, IMOD, and MIB, including the deployment of a range of AI functionalities and plugins in these platforms, using GPU resources where necessary. These containers have primarily been configured for use on STFC's DAaaS VM system for the purposes of running training courses, but have also been successfully tested on other HPC systems via Apptainer/Singularity. Testing has been performed by members of the CCP team and other prominent members of the community. At the Crick, the development focus has been on one of the major bottlenecks identified via the survey - the process of reconstructing a 3D volume from many individually acquired images, including stitching of image tiles in 2D and the subsequent alignment of these stitched slices into a 3D stack. This work makes use of scalable tools, including NGFF and the distributed processing library *dask*, collaborating with the developer of an existing python toolbox for multiview stitching. Benchmarking of the pipeline is being performed on publicly available data from the EMBL EBI-hosted EMPIAR repository. The project will be used as an exemplar workflow to demonstrate best-practice in the development of sustainable vEM analysis pipelines, with the intention of providing guidance for developers working on other tools. The software development resource provided by CoSeC has been directed towards investigating the support of a widely used tool for AI-based segmentation of vEM data: the *empanada* plugin for the python image analysis

tool *napari*. Limited resource availability has meant the primary developers have been unable to modernise the plugin to use more recent versions of *napari* and the surrounding scientific software ecosystem. Our CoSeC-based developer has been working on removing these limitations and integrating NGFF, establishing heuristics for performing similar tasks on other software in the community.

The inaugural CCP-volumeEM community meeting was held at the Francis Crick Institute on 3rd November 2025, with a total of 80 attendees (40 in-person, 40 online). Representatives from three other CCPs (CCP-EM, CCP4 and CCP-NC) gave invited talks, along with a range of other presentations introducing CCP-volumeEM and a range of vEM analysis applications. The talks were followed by a breakout session, where a number of topics were discussed around the possible future activities of the CCP.

A pilot online training course for the *napari* plugin *CLEM-Reg* was successfully held (including the use of the AI plugin *empanada*) using a docker container developed at RFI, deployed on STFC's DAaaS system with GPUs. Resources created by the CCP were also used in training courses in Naples (Italy), and Buenos Aires (Argentina).

Our survey highlighted a community interest in green-computing considerations, with two-thirds of respondents indicating that environmental impact may influence decisions on their analysis, but that most did not feel they had enough information about the topic. To begin building a knowledge base of green-computing in the context of vEM, a team member attended the CoSeC Energy Efficient Workshop in September.

An outcome of the discussions at the community event was the recognition of the need for cross-discipline terminology explainers, and to this end a glossary of computational and analysis terms is in preparation to be shared with the end-user community to help them understand technical terms that are frequently used but rarely explained.

Next steps:

The responses to our survey reinforced the perception that the current landscape of volume EM data management and analysis is very heterogeneous. Typical dataset sizes reported vary from 1-100 GB (46%), 100 GB - 1 TB (35%) and > 1 TB (17%), stored in a variety of open and proprietary formats. Due to the scale of resources required for vEM imaging, much work in this domain is typically performed by centralised facilities, reflected in the fact that 59% of survey respondents work in such environments. These institute-wide platforms frequently have to deal with a broad range of samples, using a range of different vEM imaging modalities. Currently there is little consensus on the best tools for many important tasks, leading to challenges in achieving high quality analytical outputs. Supporting a well-defined and robust set of analysis tools and workflows for these users will have a significant impact in advancing the wide range of science being performed by these teams.

Many promising software tools exist for vEM data analysis tasks such as 3D volume reconstruction, image segmentation, visualisation and morphological analysis. However, the problems encountered by the community frequently relate to the mismatch between the intended functionality provided by a tool, and the accessibility

of that functionality for end-users. Bridging this gap is a primary objective of CCP-volumeEM, empowering end-users to make use of the latest software tools via improved software development practices and training. Crucially, training should be provided both to end-users and developers to ensure long-term sustainability and evolution of the software and analysis ecosystem.

Based on the three work packages of *Community*, *Software and Data*, and *Training and Skills*, we will continue to grow the community of end-users and developers, making use of cross-cutting capabilities offered by the broader CoSeC community. Subject to funding availability, a regular annual community meeting would allow the broad CCP-volumeEM community to meet and discuss the status and plans for activities.

Opportunities to engage with related communities around data stewardship, NGFF development, AI, heterogeneous computing, and research software engineering will also help establish CCP-volumeEM in the broader context of scientific computing.

In terms of domain-specific software, CCP-volumeEM aims to continue to contribute to ongoing community efforts to incorporate modern computational methods. For example, adding vEM-relevant image processing and analysis functionalities to the NGFF ecosystem via direct contributions and supporting primary developers in applying best-practice would have significant impact for vEM and beyond. To build this community of developers, resources such training courses, tutorials and exemplar workflows will be created and maintained. Development of training courses for end-users will also be supported, working with primary developers to create robust and accessible materials where required. For accessibility and flexibility of our training offerings, we are planning to support a mixture of in-person and online training courses, with outputs being recorded where possible, and shared with curated documentation to provide persistent resources even after live events.

An important consideration in a long-term roadmap is the extremely dynamic nature of the vEM analysis domain, with new AI-based methods coming online regularly. As such, the CCP will need to remain agile to new developments that may disrupt the field. Furthermore, the CCP's relationship with adjacent and overlapping fields like cryo-EM and connectomics should be clearly established in order to work together effectively as part of the broader scientific imaging community.

CCP volumeEM

Bringing modern computational tools to the volume EM community

Community

Understand the range of stakeholders and establish the current landscape

Create and share a range of resources via various channels

Landscape

Distill the most impactful activities to benefit the community of end-users and developers

Tools

Support integration of new tools and create exemplar workflows. Create and curate robust, reproducible environments

Identify resources and funding to help provide long-term support for the community

Establish and share best practice for development and long-term maintenance of domain-critical software

Training

Guide community of researchers and developers in use and development of vEM analysis methods

UKNR

[Prof Eugene Lim](#), King's College London

The UKNR community consists of 40-50 physicists and computational scientists which includes both code-developers and code-users, based around several complementary numerical relativity (NR) codes: **GRTeclyn/GRChombo** (UK-based GRTL Collaboration), **MHDueT** (UK-led), **ETK/Carpet(X)** (international ETK Collaboration), **ExaGRyPE** (UK-based), **BAM** (open source international code) and **METHOD** (UK-based). The various parts of the UKNR community have evolved independently and are now world leaders in several high-profile areas, including signal modelling for gravitational-wave astronomy, pioneering applications of numerical relativity to cosmology, and to fundamental physics.

As a community, UKNR CCP aims to bring these separate efforts together in a coherent, supportive community, that can exploit its complementary expertise maintain and grow its international leadership to play a defining role in several major scientific challenges: the scientific exploitation of the next generation of gravitational-wave detectors on Earth and in space that will come online between 2035 and 2040. In particular, the imminent launch of the LISA mission in 2034 will require NR precision and efficiency which are unattainable with present code bases and methods.

Our website is at <https://www.uknumericalrelativity.org/>.

Update on activities that have taken place to this point:

1. **Kick-Off Townhall 26 Febuary 2025, King's College London.** This meeting kick-started the development of our community, and was attended by all key stakeholders as well as the CoSeC Director Stephen Longshaw.
2. **Gregynog International Meeting: *Towards the Next Generation*, June 17-19 2025.** This is the first of our UKNR International workshop, which was attended by a majority of UKNR members, together with international scientists and HPC stakeholders which include Mark Wilkinson (Director of DiRAC), Katherine Riley (Director of Science, Argonne National Labs), Tobias Weinzierl (EuroHPC), Shuisheng He (Chair of CCP-NTH) and others. Meeting Report is published on our website.
3. **UKNR Benchmarking Exercise:** We have begun our benchmarking exercise for UK NR codes, led by Technical Lead Miren Radia with support from Katy Clough, Mark Hannam and Eugene Lim. The goal of this exercise is to take a “screenshot” of the readiness of NR codes used (or planned to be used) by the UKNR community for present and future UK DRI. The planned benchmarked codes are (a) For CPU : ETK/Carpet, GRChombo, GRTeclyn, MHDueT, BAM, ExaGRyPE (b) For GPUs : ETK/CarpetX, GRTeclyn, MHDueT, ExaGRyPE. We have been provided with a generous allocation of 0.5M CPU/Hrs and 4500 GPU Node/Hrs from DiRAC to complete this task (Target on March 2026). We intend to compile this into a report to be released to the community (and the public).

4. **Launch of Mentorship programme:** Led by new CoSeC Fellow Miquel Miravet Tenés, we have launched a community wide mentorship programme. The goal is to provide career guidance to early career scientists and to advocate for them to the community and beyond.
5. **HPC Days Workshop:** Led by Han Zhang, UKNR organised a mini-workshop dedicated to NR at the annual HPC Days workshop at Durham.
6. **Community collaborative exchanges:** The CCP also supported intercommunity exchanges e.g. we provided funding for the visit of Rhiannon Silva (Cardiff) to QMUL as part of her training to use GRChombo. We also supported the successful application (led by Ericka Florio, Cambridge) of a CoSeC Travel Fund for a US based scientist to visit several UK NR groups and attend the UKNR Annual Meeting in Birmingham.
7. **Joint grant application:** Led by Miguel Bezares (Nottingham, MHDueT) and Katy Clough (QMUL, GRTL Collaboration), UKNR provided the framework for a joint grant application to the Software Sustainability Institute for cross-cutting code development between MHDuet and GRTEclyn, which advanced to the final round but was unfortunately unsuccessful.

Next steps:

Our long-term goal is to maintain and extend our international scientific and technical leadership in NR. This is encapsulated by a set of Community Grand Challenges. To achieve this goal, we will bring together our efforts that have evolved separately into a coherent and mutually supportive whole, in a series of Community Building Challenges. Along the way, we aim to participate in the overall strengthening of the UK DRI landscape in collaboration with other computational communities.

Community Grand Challenges:

1. **Achieving high precision with less.** We aim to achieve the precision required for the next generation GW detectors by adopting more energy efficient technologies (e.g. GPU) and code methodologies (e.g. single precision methods, more efficient code factoring).
2. **Incorporating AI and machine learning into NR.** We will investigate, and if applicable, integrate AI/ML techniques into the NR workflow. This includes investigating both PINN-based hyperbolic and elliptic solvers, using LLM for code documentation, using CNN-based techniques to populate GW output and error-correction etc.
3. **Achieving software sovereignty.** Many UK-based codes still rely on non-UK compute libraries (e.g. US ECP-based AMReX). Our long term goal is to build a UK-based capability to develop our own compute libraries for adaptive mesh finite difference solvers, in collaboration with SCD and other CoSeC CCPs which require such technologies.

Community Building Challenges:

1. **Building more coherent community:** Even though we are a community with multiple code bases, we aim to be more coherent with more code collaboration/consolidation and cross-cutting projects, including joint grant applications.
2. **Advocating as a community (“speaking with one voice”):** A key aim of the CCP is to be able to unite the voices of all the community on matters of import.
3. **Nurturing diversity and helping our members to succeed:** A great strength of our community is its diversity and its organically supportive environment. We aim to further strengthen this, with the aim of becoming a “model community”.

To do so, in the shorter term (2026-2029) we will focus on activities that will:

1. **Join up the community:** We will achieve this through broad community wide initiatives, such as the ongoing code benchmarking project and cross-cutting code collaborations (e.g. the ongoing MHDueT/GRTEclyn joint code development with shared RSEs). We have and will continue to submit joint grant applications.
2. **Build a long term sustainable and collaborative relationship with our CoSeC partners:** We will build this through joint code development projects (e.g. developing critical code infrastructure for ExaGRyPe and GRTEclyn through the 1 FTE commitment from CoSeC), and in the future through possible joint PhD supervision and regular academic exchanges. A key early challenge is that there is presently no NR expertise within CoSeC.
3. **Explore and engage with AI/ML applications in NR:** There is increasing interest within the community to engage with AI/ML techniques in NR.
4. **UKNR-CCP ASCEND position paper on UK DRI:** At the end of our Benchmarking exercise, we will undertake the writing of a “live” document on our community’s position on the present and future of UK DRI, to be submitted to ASCEND.
5. **Build partnerships with other CoSeC communities:** We understand many of the other CCPs have overlapping expertise with our community, and we intend to seek out partnerships with them in order to achieve some of our longer term goals such as software sovereignty.
6. **Strengthen and extend engagement with industry partners:** Historically, NR has strong engagement with the industry (e.g. ExaGRyPe is presently being used as a benchmark by NVIDIA and GRChombo/GRTEclyn were built with substantial involvement with INTEL engineers via the Intel IPPP at Cambridge). We will strengthen and extend this engagement.

In the longer term (2029-beyond), **a key scientific milestone will be to become “LISA ready” in 2035 and take a world leading role in future discoveries.** In addition to leading scientifically, **we aim to be in a position to develop our own compute libraries in collaboration with other CCPs,** in particular if there is a strong technological incentive to switch to single precision compute.

Roadmap for UKNR 2026-2030

CCP-TEPP

[Dr Ed Bennett](#), Swansea University

CCP-TEPP brings together the software-facing and computational parts of the particle physics community. This includes computational theoretical techniques (in particular lattice quantum field theory, which drives significant amounts of HPC resource utilisation), software supporting experiments (including detector simulation, triggering, and event generation, among other aspects), and computation supporting areas that bridge theory and experiment (such as phenomenology). It aims to also support particle physics-adjacent work where there is overlap, such as astroparticle physics.

The primary aim of the community is to ensure that the software in use in particle physics is capable of delivering the scientific aims of the wider field. A particular challenge, for example, is ensuring that the data collection and analysis pipelines are ready to cope with the increase in data production rate expected from the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider. A second aim is to increase the amount to which particle physicists from different subdisciplines discuss and share knowledge about software development, and thereby to help address skills gaps and enable improvement of software quality across the field.

Being a scoping project rather than fully approved and commissioned CCP, we did not initially consider it appropriate to set up a website or social media channels. If CoSeC recommends this, then we will prioritise it as our first action in 2026.

Update on activities that have taken place to this point:

During 2025, the following activities have taken place:

Scoping workshops

- [CCP-TEPP Scoping workshop for computational theoretical particle physics](#). University of Edinburgh, April 2025.
- [CCP-TEPP Scoping workshop for computational experimental particle physics](#). University of Warwick, June 2025.

At these events, discussions were held with representatives from across the UK particle physics software community, identifying areas of commonality and difference, probing directions of travel, and laying the groundwork for the preparation of the CCP-TEPP roadmap document.

- [CCP-TEPP Knowledge exchange workshop for computational particle physics](#). Daresbury Laboratory, September 2025.

Building on the results of the discussions and the draft roadmap, this event brought together participants from all career stages in particle physics to discuss common challenges. Presentations included perspectives experiment, theory, professional research software engineering, and industry; topics discussed included hardware and software infrastructure; accelerators and performance portability; reproducible data analysis and workflow management; documentation, testing, and code quality of

software; machine learning and artificial intelligence; and quantum computing. All of these are areas identified as growth opportunities that the majority of the field has in common.

- Based on the input from the above events, a draft roadmap document has been prepared. This is currently in review before being released.

In addition, project lead Bennett has participated in the following CoSeC events in-person, funded by the project:

- CoSeC Community Forum, Sheffield, June 2025
- CoSeC Conference, Manchester, December 2025

Next steps:

Over the course of 2025 we have held a number of workshops with the particle physics software community to understand the state of the landscape, resulting in a draft landscape analysis/roadmap document, a draft of which is attached.

Some of the key take-aways are summarised in the graphic below; we try and draw out some of the key points in the remaining space here.

The ultimate challenge for the particle physics community is to understand the laws governing reality at the lowest levels; this includes the three STFC key science challenge problems: *What are the fundamental particles and fields?*, *What are the fundamental laws and symmetries of physics?* and *Why is there more matter than antimatter*. These are clearly unlikely to be solved in five years or in the UK alone. Within the experimental sub-community, much effort is currently being focused towards the upcoming upgrade to the Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), which will increase the data production rate such that the data acquisition and processing pipelines must have an order of magnitude higher throughput. The theory community has less of a unifying focus, with many scientific challenges being addressed concurrently, but using the same underpinning techniques and software tools.

All parts of the TEPP software community have pockets of deep technical knowledge; one goal that was identified was to better spread this, and more generally increase the maintainability of the software such that it is less reliant on single individuals and is more approachable to experienced developers seeing it for the first time.

The increasing move to GPU-based compute is increasingly targeted by most of the community; where there are codes still reliant on CPU, supporting users in either porting this or migrating to alternative GPU-enabled solutions will future-proof the research for next-generation resources.

CCP-TEPP ROADMAP

Towards a Collaborative Computational Project in Theoretical and Experimental Particle Physics

Engagement

A series of workshops to identify community directions and needs

A set of communities with many pockets of deep technical knowledge

Knowledge exchange workshops ensure that the benefits of technical improvements are shared across the community

Community documentation writing events will improve maintainability and provide an on-ramp to supporting RSEs

Support more code becoming open source to increase reproducibility and impact

CoSeC technical work

Targeted interventions in community software address cross-discipline challenges, including interoperability, documentation, and openness.

GPU transition

The shift to accelerated HPC is a key driver of code evolution. GPUs are also needed in experimental pipelines to enable faster throughput

HL-LHC switch-on

The HL-LHC, expected to start taking data in 2030, will generate an order of magnitude more data per second than previous runs. Data collection and analysis pipelines must be ready for this.

Enable greater sharing of data infrastructure to allow greater data sharing by theorists

A community with increased technical skill sharing, producing more maintainable software

**Computational Science Centre
for Research Communities**

Report produced by Damian Jones
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